

TOWARDS THE VISION 2030

The Zambia We Want “Moving Towards Vision 2030” Strategic Framework

Naomi Banda

**SOLAR ENERGY SOLUTIONS FOR ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT**

Table of Contents

1.0 Executive Summary	4
1.2 Introduction.....	5
1.3 How Electricity Drives Economic Growth	5
1.31 Industrial Productivity:	5
1.32 Technological Advancement:	5
1.33 Socioeconomic Development:	5
1.34 Infrastructure and Public Services:	5
1.35 Stimulates Commerce and Trade:.....	5
The Relationship Between Electricity and GDP	6
1.41 A Key Indicator:.....	6
1.5 Policy Focus:	6
2.30 Why Financing Smart Power Systems is the Next Strategic Frontier	11
2.31 Changes in Global Electricity Generation 2022-2026	11
2.32 Growing weather impacts on power systems highlight the importance of investing in electricity security	12
3.0 Where do we want to be?	13
4.12 Sub-Sector Best Prospects	15
Solar Power:	15
4.13. Solar Energy Opportunities.....	15
3.7 Implication of Adopting “Vision 2030 Energy Transition” Phase of System Integration	16
3.8 From Passive Demand to Load shaping	18
4.0 Multiple Deployment Opportunities for Large-Scale Storage	19
4.1 Optimising the use of PSH	20
5.2 Engaging Distributed Battery Storage.....	21
6.0 Facility Location, Design and Layout	22
6.1 Power System Flexibility	23
6.2 Power System Flexibility is a Concept that is much Broader Than Power Plant Flexibility.	24
6.3 Phases of VRE Integration.....	25
6.4 Priority Areas for System Transformation	26
6.6 Modelling Approach: Zambia Will Follow China’s Blue Print Standing on the Shoulder’s of Giants	28
6.7 Spot markets and regional trade	30
6.8 Advanced Power System Flexibility	30
6.8 Advanced Technologies Enabled by Digitalisation – Reduce the Need to rely on Power Plants To Provide Flexibility.....	31
6.91 Renewable energy policy.....	32
7.0 Long-term strategy	34

7.1	Demand Side Management/Demand Side Response	34
7.3	Electricity storage: Benchmarking China’s Move	35
7.4	Standing on The Shoulders of Giants Investing in the 100Kva Battery Inverter Packages	36
7.5	Aggregate Planning for Increased Capacity Alternatives 1000MW/ 500MW/ 250 MW Vision 2030 ...	37
7.6	Towards Vision 2030 Budget Estimate Plan A	38
5.2	Generation Capacity per Inverter	38
7.7	Budget Estimation Plan B: Capacity 500MW by 2030	39
7.8	Generation Capacity per Unit	40
7.9	Budget Estimation Plan C: Capacity 250MW by 2030	41
8.0	Generation Capacity per Inverter	42
8.1	Labour Planning	43
8.2	Employment Stability Process	43
8.3	Hold Employment Constant.....	43
8.4	Work Schedules	43
9.0	Job Design.....	43
9.1	Plant Maintenance and Reliability Scheduling.....	43
9.2	How Do We Get There?	44
9.3	Investing Decisions: Surety Bonds & Renewable Energy Projects	44
9.4	Energy Storage Projects	44
9.5	Power Purchase Agreements: This Power Purchase Agreement will be Between The State Financers (The Obligee NAPSA, Private and Public Sector Banks / Private Parties as Investors and Bank of Zambia as Issuer and Underwriting Authority (The Surety) with the Off-Taker ZESCO as the Principal)	44
9.6	Decommissioning Bonds:.....	45
9.7	Supply / Material Procurement:	45
9.8	Interconnection Agreement :	45
9.9	Financing Decisions.....	46
	Public Sector Debt Funding.....	46
10.0	The Central Bank to Implement Surety Bonds.....	47
10.1	What Is a Surety Bond and How Are the Parties Involved Defined?	47
10.2	What Are the Obligations of Each Party To the Bond?	47
10.4	Which Laws Require Bonding?.....	47
10.5	What Are Attorney-in-Fact and Power of Attorney - Bank of Zambia	48
10.6	What Happens with a Claim on a Surety Bond?	48
10.7	What Are Rights of Subrogation?	48
10.81	What Is a General Indemnity Agreement?	49
10.9	What Legal Benefits Does a Bond Provide Subcontractors?.....	49
11.0	Financing Structure For Vision 2030 – Surety Green Bonds.....	50
11.01	Issuance (Proposed Issuer is Bank of Zambia) :	50

11.2 Investment (The National Pensions Scheme Authority, State Owned Banks and Private Sector Banks are Target Investors):.....	50
11.3 Earmarked Funds:	50
11.4 Returns:	50
12.0 Transparency and Reporting:	50
13.0 Purpose of Green Bonds	51
14. Conclusion	51
References	52

1.0 Executive Summary

Zambia has been experiencing extreme weather events, particularly droughts, floods, shortened rainy seasons, high temperatures, and frequent zoonotic, human, and food crop diseases. These events have put adaptation and mitigation on the policy map (Kalaba et al., 2022). The role of renewable energy has increasingly featured in policy discussions to reduce deforestation and forest degradation to build community resilience and climate change adaptive capacities and to drive socio-economic development (Kalaba et al., 2022).

Total population experiencing energy poverty by region

The Sub-Saharan region in which Zambia lies experiences energy poverty with some areas having no access, unreliable electricity and underserved sectors. This necessitates initiatives to diversify away from the existing systems to integrated systems. To prepare for the future, it is important for us to find a strategic framework that will not only work for the future but also help the situation now. Zambia does not have to do this in isolation but benchmark existing frameworks applied by other countries that have done it and succeeded like China. China's 5year strategic plans provided policy guidelines on how to navigate the challenges Zambia and other countries in the Sub- Saharan region face with energy and sustainability. In this report we will review some strategies, their implication and attempt to make suggestions on what Zambia can implement to deal with the energy crisis that is turning into a nightmare for policymakers, suppliers and consumers.

1.2 Introduction

Electricity is vital for economic growth because it powers modern infrastructure, enables productivity in industries, and facilitates socioeconomic activities, all of which drive economic development. Industries, transportation, communication, and even healthcare rely on consistent electricity to function and innovate, making it a fundamental input for a prosperous economy.

1.3 How Electricity Drives Economic Growth

1.31 Industrial Productivity:

Electricity is a core input for modern industrial processes, enabling the operation of machinery and technology essential for production.

1.32 Technological Advancement:

Access to electricity is crucial for operating the advanced electronics and computers that underpin innovation and new economic models.

1.33 Socioeconomic Development:

In developing nations, electricity provides access to lighting, heating, and cooling, and supports activities like employment, trade, and agricultural production.

1.34 Infrastructure and Public Services:

Reliable electricity powers essential infrastructure like airports and hospitals, ensuring safety and functionality in critical sectors.

1.35 Stimulates Commerce and Trade:

Electricity is necessary for the operation of businesses, markets, and transportation networks that facilitate commerce and trade, leading to economic expansion.

The Relationship Between Electricity and GDP

1.41 A Key Indicator:

Studies have shown a strong, often causal, relationship between electricity consumption and a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). High rates of electricity consumption are typically needed to achieve and sustain high rates of economic growth.

1.5 Policy Focus:

For policymakers, understanding this relationship is crucial for designing strategies to promote economic growth and stability through improved electricity access and reliability.

2.0 Zambia and Energy Where Are We Now?

As at 2021, Zambia falls in the “Have not reached Modern Energy Minimum”, on world records depicted above (*THE POWER SYSTEM IN ENERGY-POOR*, n.d.).

Currently, global electricity production relies heavily on fossil fuels like coal, oil, and gas, with renewables and nuclear power making up a smaller portion. The desired state is a shift towards a more sustainable, secure, and stable electricity future, driven by low-carbon, renewable sources like solar, wind, and hydro, alongside advancements in nuclear, geothermal, and energy storage technologies. This will be achieved by investing in these clean energy technologies, modernizing grid infrastructure, and implementing policies that encourage the transition away from carbon-intensive energy production.

2.1 Zambia's Production Capacity

As of the first half of 2024, Zambia's installed electricity generation capacity was approximately 3,777 Megawatts (MW), with the majority being hydropower. However, a reduction in power generation due to drought in the 2023/2024 season has led to a significant power deficit, with available power generation at only 1,040 MW in July 2024, resulting in a

net deficit of 950 MW even with imports. This situation is being addressed through efforts like adding solar capacity and managing demand to minimize interruptions to economic activity.

Table 2: National installed generation capacity by technology as of 31 December 2022. Source: ERB, 2023.

Technology	Capacity (MW)
Hydro	3163.44
Coal	330
HFO	110
Solar	89.06
Diesel	84.8
Total	3777.3

2.12 Installed Capacity:

Around 3,777 MW, growing slightly from 2023 due to new solar plants.

2.13 Dominant Source:

Hydropower still accounts for the largest share, though its output is affected by drought.

2.14 Available Power:

A significant drop in available power generation occurred in the first half of 2024, falling to 1,040 MW in July.

2.15 Power Deficit:

A deficit of 1,360 MW existed in July 2024, with a net deficit of 950 MW after importing power.

2.2 Factors Contributing to the Current Situation:

2.21 Drought:

The 2023/2024 rain season has negatively impacted hydropower output, a primary source of electricity.

2.22 Increased Demand:

Growing demand from mining, industry, and expanding access to electricity contribute to the challenges of meeting national needs.

2.23 Uncertainty in Demand:

Fluctuations in industrial demand and the potential for customers to switch to alternative sources, like private solar, make forecasting difficult.

2.24 Efforts to Address the Deficit:

2.25 Adding Solar Capacity:

New solar power plants are being commissioned to diversify the energy mix and increase generation.

2.26 Demand-Side Management:

The government is implementing measures to manage electricity consumption and shift load away from peak demand periods.

2.27 Seeking New Projects:

Plans are underway for new large hydropower projects, such as Batoka Gorge, and smaller rural electrification projects to expand capacity in the long term.

2.28 ZESCO and Its Role in Electricity Production and Supply is Falling Short

ZESCO, a vertically integrated parastatal utility, operates government-owned power stations, and is responsible for maintaining and installing transmission lines and distribution networks. Zambia's electricity market is structured as a single-buyer market, with ZESCO acting as the sole off-taker and bulk retailer of electricity through the national grid. Independent Power Producers (IPPs) operate their own assets and generate electricity, however, to distribute it via the grid, they must sell the electricity to ZESCO through Power Purchase Agreements (PPA). Off-grid IPPs can operate and distribute independently. Zambia's main hydroelectric power facilities are the Kariba North Bank Power Station (1,080 MW), Kafue Gorge Power Station (980MW), Kafue Gorge Lower Power Station (750 MW), Victoria Falls Power Station (108 MW), Lunsemfwa Hydro Power Station (56 MW), and the Itezhi Tezhi Hydro Power Station (120 MW). Maamba Collieries Limited

operates Zambia’s largest IPP, a coal-fired thermal power plant commissioned in 2016, which can generate up to 300 MW. Zambia’s installed solar capacity is 89 MW. Zambia has two utility scale solar power plants: French company, Neoen, and U.S. company, First Solar, own and operate the 47.5 MW Bangweulu Solar Power Station in Lusaka, of which the Zambian government holds a 20 percent stake through its Industrial Development Corporation (IDC). Italian firm, Enel Green Power, owns and operates the 34 MW Ngonye Solar Power Station, in Lusaka Province.

2.29 Challenges of Where We Are Now

There is no diversification of the key economic sector in key areas as depicted by the 8th National Development Plan (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022). The aim of the government is economic transformation depicted below.

Figure 1: The Change Process Envisioned in the Plan

Image Obtained from (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022).

Following the 8th National Development Plan, the mandate to solve the energy crisis must remain top priority because energy is at the core of development. Zambia ranks among countries that have not reached Modern Energy Minimum and is classified as poor according to the report and appendix following (*THE POWER SYSTEM IN ENERGY-POOR*, n.d.). Ranked as under modern energy minimum with unreliable grid and access deficit.

Appendix

75 Countries that have not reached Modern Energy Minimum (We classify these as Energy-Poor)

	COUNTRY	UNDER MODERN ENERGY MINIMUM	UNRELIABLE GRID	ACCESS DEFICIT
Sub-Saharan Africa	Zambia	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Zimbabwe	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Angola	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Benin	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Côte d'Ivoire	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Cameroon	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Congo (Brazzaville)	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	DRC	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Eritrea	Yes	No	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Ethiopia	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Ghana	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Kenya	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Mozambique	Yes	No	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Niger	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Nigeria	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Sudan	Yes	No	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Senegal	Yes	No	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	South Sudan	Yes	No	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Togo	Yes	No	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Tanzania	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Burundi	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Burkina Faso	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	CAR	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Comoros	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Cabo Verde	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Guinea	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Gambia, The	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Guinea-Bissau	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sub-Saharan Africa	Liberia	Yes	Yes	Yes

Image obtained from (*THE POWER SYSTEM IN ENERGY-POOR*, n.d.).

2.30 Why Financing Smart Power Systems is the Next Strategic Frontier

Emerging and developing economies are the engines of global electricity demand growth. About 85% of additional electricity demand through 2026 is set to come from outside advanced economies, with China contributing substantially even as the country's economy undergoes structural changes (Jiang et al., 123 C.E.).

2.31 Changes in Global Electricity Generation 2022-2026

Renewables are set to provide more than one-third of total electricity generation globally by early 2025, overtaking coal. The share of renewables in electricity generation is forecast to rise from 30% in 2023 to 37% in 2026, with the growth largely supported by the expansion of solar

PV. Through this period, renewables are set to more than offset demand growth in advanced economies such as the United States and the European Union, displacing fossil-fired supply.

2.32 Growing weather impacts on power systems highlight the importance of investing in electricity security

Global hydropower generation declined in 2023 due to weather impacts such as droughts, below average rainfall and early snowmelts in numerous regions. Canada, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, India, Mexico, Türkiye, the United States, and Vietnam, along with other countries, all saw hydropower generation decline. The global hydropower capacity factor, a key measure of utilisation rate, fell to below 40%, the lowest value recorded in at least three decades. In certain countries, diminished hydropower output led to energy shortages, heightened reliance on fossil sources such as coal and gas, and raised concerns about the stability of electricity supply. The overall trend underscores the susceptibility of hydropower to weather patterns and the potential exposure of countries that rely heavily on hydro to generate electricity. Diversifying energy sources, building regional power interconnections and implementing strategies for resilient generation in the face of changing weather patterns will be increasingly important.

3.0 Where do we want to be?

Vision 2030 Energy Transition

Extreme weather events triggered major power outages in 2023 in the United States and India. This underlined the need to boost resilience as weather impacts on power systems increase, with both supply and demand becoming more weather-dependent. Insufficient power capacity, fuel supply challenges and grid-related technical issues also continued to cause significant power shortages in many regions. The majority of these outages were observed in emerging economies such as Pakistan, Kenya, Nigeria, and Zambia which are particularly affected by insufficient electricity supply, infrastructure problems and strained grids in the face of rising power demand. Expanded, stronger grids would not only ensure reliable electricity but also serve as a vital backbone for integrating renewables into power systems. Improving data collection, digitalisation and greater data transparency regarding outages is also essential to provide better insight into why faults occurred and to help develop preventative measures.

Image Obtained fom: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-australia-42190358>

Specific operating measures and new markets for ensuring the stability of power systems are becoming more common. Countries with high shares of variable renewable generation are implementing mechanisms to ensure a steady power system frequency. Some regions are establishing minimum requirements for system inertia, a property typically provided by conventional generators with spinning rotors that helps enhance the power system's resilience during disturbances. Additionally, various countries including the United Kingdom, Ireland and Australia have been introducing markets and measures such as fast frequency response and similar services that stabilise the power system rapidly after disruptions. Battery storage

systems can provide such services for grid stability while enhancing system flexibility, thus playing a crucial role in integrating renewable energy sources.

3.1 Key Reforms To Support The Macro Economic Objectives

The 8th National Development Plan outlined that Over the Plan period, the Government will implement the following reforms to achieve the set macroeconomic objectives:

3.2 Strengthen Public Finance Management:

This will be a central Strategic Development Area to restoring budget credibility, improving the efficiency of public expenditures, and supporting private sector-led growth. The goals of Public Finance Management are enhancing domestic resource mobilization, increasing the efficiency of public expenditure, halting the accumulation of arrears and improving fiscal transparency (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022). The Government will also ensure adherence to the legal provisions and guidelines on public investment management as well as enforce the penalty regime in both the Public Finance Management Act and the Public Procurement Act (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022).

3.3 Establish a Fiscal Risk Management Framework:

In light of slowing growth, tighter fiscal conditions, and growing debt burden, the Government will closely monitor fiscal risks by developing a risk monitoring framework to anticipate expenditure pressures and revenue shocks (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022).

3.4 Strengthen the Legal Framework for Public Private Partnership:

To leverage on public private partnership (PPP) financing for developmental projects, the Public-Private Partnership Act No. 14 of 2009 will be revised to, among others, strengthen the framework for managing fiscal risks, such as fiscal commitments and potential contingent liabilities (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022). In addition, the management of unsolicited proposals and state-owned enterprise (SOE)-implemented PPPs will be improved (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022). These changes are intended to support the delivery of cost-effective and sustainable infrastructure projects.

4.0 Undertake Energy Sector Reforms:

In the electricity sub-sector, reforms will focus on enhancing the operational efficiency of ZESCO including its cost structure.

4.1 Implication

4.12 Sub-Sector Best Prospects

Solar Power:

Zambia has abundant potential to generate additional solar power as it possesses ample and intense sunlight, averaging about 2,000 - 3,000 hours of sunshine per year.

4.13. Solar Energy Opportunities

Given Zambia's continually growing power needs, for commercial and residential use, and ability to export through the Southern Africa Power Pool, there are significant investment opportunities in on- and off-grid power generation, particularly with regards to renewable energy sources.

There are opportunities in electricity generation and transmission, storage, particularly with regards to renewable energy sources. While Zambia has the potential to generate 2,300 MW of solar and 3,000 MW of wind, only 176 MW of solar has been installed with Chisamba Plant generating a capacity of 100MW and there is no wind power to date.

Diversify away from hydro power. The alternatives for solar energy adoption plans have been outlined in this document considering relevant costs. The plans proposed do not include set up or installation cost. We recommend recruitment and training of local talent engineers and electricians to work on the project proposed for the purpose of job creation and skills development. The suppliers of the utility will be responsible for providing after sale service in order to equip local engineers with speciality knowledge of installation, monitoring and maintenance of the facilities.

3.5 Proposed Reform: Surety Bond Law Enactment for Long Term National Projects to Protect Investors Against Risks.

3.51. What is a Surety Bond?

Three-party instrument: Principal/Contractor (obligor), Beneficiary/Owner (obligee), Surety/Insurer (guarantor).

Guarantees performance obligations (*Bond Management Services*, n.d.).

Bank of Zambia to issue surety bonds and act as surety where financial institutions act as the owner's by investing and ZESCO will be used as the contractor principal for the "Vision 2030 Transition Energy" Project.

3.7 Implication of Adopting "Vision 2030 Energy Transition" Phase of System Integration

The properties of VRE interact with the broader power system, which gives rise to a number of relevant integration effects. These effects do not appear abruptly, but rather increase over time along with the increase in VRE penetration. The IEA has developed a phase categorisation to capture changing impacts on the power system and resulting integration issues:

Phase 1: The first set of VRE plants are deployed, but they are basically insignificant at the system level; effects are very localised, for example at the grid connection point of plants.

Phase 2: As more VRE plants are added, changes between load and net load become noticeable. Upgrades to operating practices and making better use of existing system resources are usually sufficient to achieve system integration.

Phase 3: Greater swings in the supply–demand balance prompt the need for a systematic increase in power system flexibility that goes beyond what can be fairly easily supplied by existing assets and operational practice.

Phase 4: VRE output is sufficient to provide a large majority of electricity demand during certain periods (high VRE generation during times of low demand); this requires changes in

both operational and regulatory approaches. From the operational perspective, it is related to the way the power system responds immediately following system disturbances. This phase thus concerns power system stability. From the regulatory perspective, it may involve rule changes so that VRE has to provide frequency response services such as primary and secondary frequency regulation.

Phase 5: Without additional measures, adding more VRE plants means that their output frequently exceeds power demand and structural surpluses of negative net load appear, leading to an increased risk of curtailment of VRE output. Shifting demand to periods of high VRE output and creating new demand via electrification can mitigate this issue. Another possibility is to enhance interchange with neighbouring systems. In this phase it is possible that, in some periods, demand is entirely covered by VRE without any solar plants on the high-voltage grid.

Phase 6: The main obstacle to achieving even higher shares of VRE now becomes meeting demand during periods of low sun availability over extended periods (e.g. weeks), as well as supplying uses that cannot be easily electrified. Most countries around the world are currently in Phases 1 and 2. However, as VRE deployment accelerates over the coming five years, this will shift with more and more countries moving into Phases 3 and 4. It is important to note that a country-wide characterisation especially for large and diverse countries can provide only a rough indication.

Table 5. Different timescales of power system flexibility

Flexibility type	Ultra-short-term flexibility/stability	Very short-term flexibility	Short-term flexibility	Medium-term flexibility	Long-term flexibility	Very long-term flexibility
Timescale	Subseconds to seconds	Seconds to minutes	Minutes to hours	Hours to days	Days to months	Months to years
Issue	Ensuring system stability (voltage and frequency stability) at high shares of non-synchronous generation	Ensuring short-term frequency control at high shares of variable generation	Meeting more frequent, rapid and less predictable changes in the supply-demand balance; system regulation	Determining operation schedule of the available generation resources to meet system conditions in hour- and day-ahead time frame	Addressing longer periods of surplus or deficit of variable generation, mainly driven by presence of a specific weather system	Balancing seasonal and inter-annual availability of variable generation with power demand
Has relevance for following areas of system operation and planning	Dynamic stability (inertia response, grid strength)	Primary and secondary frequency response, which include AGC	AGC, ED, balancing real-time market, regulation	ED for hour-ahead, UC for day-ahead time frame	UC, scheduling, adequacy	Hydro-thermal co-ordination, adequacy, power system planning

Notes: AGC = automatic generation control; ED = economic dispatch; UC = unit commitment.
 Source: IEA (2018a), *Status of Power System Transformation 2018: Advanced Power Plant Flexibility*.

3.8 From Passive Demand to Load shaping

In the context of power system transformation, it is useful to consider a generalised concept of demand-side integration, which goes beyond the standard concepts of demand response and management and takes a fresh look at energy efficiency. Essentially, growing shares of VRE can be integrated into power systems by better matching electricity demand to an increasingly variable supply. This is possible not only via dynamic shifts in electricity consumption, but more generally by any intervention that shapes demand to better match available supply. This can be achieved in four different ways:

1. Dynamic Shifting of Load.

This type of load shaping takes into account short-term or real-time information and control signals to adjust consumption. Most importantly, this type of load shaping does not reduce total consumption, but shifts the time when it occurs.

2. **Dynamic load curtailment.** In contrast to dynamic load shifting, dynamic load curtailment reduces power demand during critical hours, without recovering this demand later. One example would be a temporary halt of production during times of very high electricity prices. This can be profitable for a consumer if the cost of electricity exceeds the value added of the process for several hours.
3. **Structural Reductions in Electricity Demand via Energy Efficiency.** This can be achieved, for example, by replacement of less efficient lighting in residential buildings with light emitting diodes (LEDs), which leads to a structural load reduction that is concentrated in hours of low or no sunlight. Hence, such measures naturally improve the match of load with the output profile of solar PV.
4. **Structural Increases in Electricity Demand via Electrification.** As introduced in the section on phases of system integration, at Phase 5 and beyond structural surpluses of VRE emerge. These are concentrated during the middle of the day for solar PV. In the absence of electricity demand during such periods, VRE output will need to be curtailed and the market price and value of VRE will be very low. Hence, increasing demand through electrification of industry, heating or transport can reduce curtailment, although Power-to-X can also provide viable options for system integration.

4.0 Multiple Deployment Opportunities for Large-Scale Storage

Electricity storage describes all technologies that can absorb electrical energy and return it as electrical energy at a later stage. Electricity storage technologies can provide multiple services ranging from fast frequency response to bulk energy storage, which cover timescales from ultra-short- to long-term and which help to accommodate new challenges related to VRE variability. This makes them suited to providing different aspects of the range of services electricity storage can provide. Recently, battery storage technologies have seen rapid cost declines, and although not suitable for seasonal storage, could play a greater flexibility role in the short term in future power systems.

Table 7. Qualitative description of energy storage services in the power system

	Application	Description
Generation	RE integration – Bulk	Time shift RE output to optimise for grid integration and minimise curtailment
	RE integration – Ramp	Optimise short-term RE output to improve power quality and avoid imbalances
Network operation	Frequency control	Maintain supply and demand balance via power increase/decrease with different response patterns
	T&D deferral	Defer upgrades in network infrastructure
	T&D congestion	Avoid re-dispatch or local price differences due to risk of overloading existing infrastructure
	Black start	Restore power plant operations after network outage without external power supply
	Voltage support	Maintain voltage levels across networks via reactive power supply/reduction
Consumption	Peak power supply	Reduce demand supplied by the network during peak hours to reduce network charges
	Back-up power	Provide power during network failure to ensure power quality and availability
	RE self-consumption	Maximise usage of self-generated power and minimise exports to the network
	Bill management	Shift energy consumption from high-tariff to low-tariff periods to reduce energy charges
Market	Energy arbitrage	Purchase power in low and sell in high price periods on wholesale or retail market

Notes: RE = renewable energy; T&D = transmission and distribution.

4.1 Optimising the use of PSH

PSH is currently the most mature and widespread technology for electricity storage. Globally, 153 GW of capacity are installed, of which 29 GW are located in China. While future expansion is limited by the availability of suitable sites and public acceptance issues in a number of countries, PSH is expected to increase by 26 GW over the period 2018–23 (IEA, 2018c). PSH can provide a variety of services to the grid, including all types of short-term and medium-term flexibility services. Due to the technological maturity of this option, future cost reduction potential is limited. However increasing system flexibility needs may bring about new opportunities for deploying PSH, through modernisation and conversion.

Embracing the versatility of grid-scale batteries as an inverter-based technology, one advantage of battery storage is its ability to adjust output upwards or downwards very quickly and precisely. Its main constraint is its operating range and duration of response, depending on the state of charge at dispatch. Due to its technical versatility, battery storage can be deployed for a number of system flexibility needs, ranging from rapid ramping in response to sudden peaks in demand, to ultra-short-term flexibility. No single application requires the entire storage technology’s capacity continuously. Therefore, idle capacity can be used to provide additional services, effectively revenue stacking and increasing the likelihood of making electricity storage profitable.

To enable revenues to flow from serving various system needs, policy makers need to remove existing barriers, for example adjusting minimum bidding size in reserve markets, where batteries could be excluded due to small size (Stephan et al., 2016). In the United States, this has been enabled by FERC ruling 841. Internationally, the deployment of battery storage varies both by size and application. Very large-scale batteries above 5 MW represent a greater share of installed battery capacity in Europe. This is due to a number of reasons. For example, in Northern Germany pilot projects for large batteries have been seen as an alternative to relieve the grid in areas with high wind penetration. Installed in 2014 with an original 5 MW of output, WEMAG's Schwerin battery project was expanded in 2017 by a further 10 MW in order to provide frequency regulation and balance the output of about 800 MW of installed wind generation in the region.

Large battery storage is also relevant in the United Kingdom where, until recently, they were encouraged to participate in the country's capacity market. Owned and operated by Staterra Energy, the Pelham battery storage power plant was commissioned in 2017. With an output of 49 MW, it is able to extract revenues from frequency regulation as well as the capacity market. Outside Europe a number of very large battery storage projects serve very specific needs. With 100 MW, the Hornsdale battery project in Australia is the largest grid-interactive battery storage facility in the world and is further example of revenue stacking, accessing both the wholesale and frequency regulation markets.

5.2 Engaging Distributed Battery Storage

Similar to distributed generation, distributed storage systems are connected at the distribution level or sited locally to serve specific needs, for example through collocation with small-scale or remote wind generation. A growing field in the deployment of battery storage relates to the provision of various grid services. Due to their speed and precision of response, batteries can be deployed for a number of applications, such as frequency regulation. Additionally, depending on the jurisdiction, battery storage may be used for a number of applications such as arbitrage in wholesale markets or for balancing markets. Depending on the frameworks available, it may be possible to deploy existing back-up batteries or even make use of EV fleets. In all of these cases, the regulatory framework and interconnection requirements play a key role for profitability.

In Germany, for example, transmission system operators (TSOs) who are in charge of procuring primary frequency reserves for very short-term flexibility have developed a set of minimum requirements, specifying the secure operating range for primary regulation provision based on the state of charge at the time of dispatch (Regelleistung, 2015). In the United Kingdom, by contrast, the attractiveness of battery storage participation in the capacity mechanism has reduced substantially due to the introduction of a new de-rating methodology, thus motivating battery operators to seek additional sources of revenue, such as the balancing mechanism. Further to these applications, typically in markets operated by the TSO or independent system operator (ISO), batteries can be deployed at the consumer end to reduce energy bills and potentially to balance the transmission or distribution networks directly. In these cases, the structures of ownership and operation depend heavily on unbundling regulations and the ability to stack revenues from different sources.

6.0 Facility Location, Design and Layout

Decentralization of Solar Plant By: Province, District or Demand

Zambia has 115 districts and 10 provinces. The locational decision of the battery energy storage solution is dependent on the layout design and location factors and cost estimates.

Zambia's "Vision 2030 Energy Transition Layout Design"

Figure 1. Illustration of an interconnected energy system enabled by digitalisation

Source: IEA (2017d), *Digitalisation and Energy*.

Digital technologies enable a multi-directional and highly integrated energy system. Pre-digital

6.1 Power System Flexibility

Power system flexibility: a concept that goes beyond power plant flexibility and is the crucial element for a successful transformation of the power system at growing proportions of solar power. Driven in many contexts by a higher share of VRE in daily operations, power system flexibility is an increasingly important topic for policy makers and system planners to consider. It is a core aspect of power system transformation, and is crucial for ensuring electricity security in modern power systems (*China Power System Transformation*, n.d.).

Power system flexibility is defined as the ability of a power system to reliably and cost effectively manage the variability and uncertainty of demand and supply across all relevant timescales, from ensuring instantaneous stability of the power system to supporting long-term security of supply. A lack of system flexibility can reduce the resilience of power systems, or lead to the loss of substantial amounts of clean electricity through curtailment of VRE. Importantly, power systems are already designed with the flexibility to manage variability and uncertainty, but requirements may grow and change over time. A number of operational, policy and investment-based interventions are available to make modern systems more flexible, facilitating cleaner, more reliable, more resilient and more affordable power systems (*China Power System Transformation*, n.d.).

6.2 Power System Flexibility is a Concept that is much Broader Than Power Plant Flexibility.

It encompasses all resources of the power system that allow for its efficient and reliable operation at growing shares of variability and uncertainty. Apart from power plants, it can be provided by grid infrastructure, demand-side response and electricity storage. In a transformed power system with higher shares of VRE, the importance of flexibility options beyond power plants increases sharply. This can open synergies with other developments in the power sector, such as the deployment of EVs.

6.3 Phases of VRE Integration

Different levels of VRE penetration require an evolving approach to providing power system flexibility. As VRE penetration increases, ensuring cost-effective and reliable integration may change flexibility requirements. The International Energy Agency (IEA) has developed a phase categorisation to capture changing impacts on the power system and resulting integration issues. This framework can be used to prioritise different measures for power system transformation. The phases are:

- **Phase 1:** The first set of VRE plants are deployed, but they are essentially insignificant at the system level; integration effects are highly localised, for example at the grid connection point of plants. Korea, the Russian Federation (“Russia”) or South Africa are examples of Phase 1 countries.

- **Phase 2:**
As more VRE plants are added, changes between load and net load become noticeable. Upgrades to operating practices and making better use of existing power system flexibility resources are usually sufficient to achieve system integration. On a national level China is currently in Phase 2. Other countries in Phase 2 include India, Japan and the United States.

- **Phase 3:** Greater swings in the supply–demand balance prompt the need for a systematic increase in power system flexibility that goes beyond what can be fairly easily supplied by existing assets and operational practice. Examples of countries in this Phase include Germany, Italy and the United Kingdom. The Chinese provinces of Xinjiang, Ningxia, Gansu and Qinghai are also considered to be currently in Phase 3.

- **Phase 4:** VRE output is sufficient to provide a large majority of electricity demand during certain periods (e.g. high VRE generation during periods of low demand); this requires changes to both operational and regulatory approaches to preserve power system stability. From the operational perspective, changes may be needed to the way the power system responds immediately following system disturbances. From the regulatory perspective, rule changes may be required to ensure that VRE has to provide

frequency response services such as primary and secondary frequency regulation. Only very few countries are in this Phase including Ireland and Denmark.

- **Phase 5:** Without additional power system flexibility measures, adding more VRE plants in this phase may mean that aggregate VRE output frequently exceeds power demand and structural surpluses of VRE appear, leading to an increased risk of curtailment of VRE output. Shifting demand to periods of high VRE output via storage or responsive demand side resources, and/or creating new demand via electrification, may mitigate this issue. Another possibility is to enhance power trading with neighbouring systems. In this phase it is possible that, in some periods, demand is entirely covered by VRE without any thermal plants on the high-voltage grid. No countries are currently in this phase.
- **Phase 6:** Once this phase is reached, the remaining obstacle to achieving even higher shares of VRE now becomes meeting demand during periods of low wind and sun availability over extended periods (e.g. weeks), as well as supplying uses that cannot be easily electrified. This phase can thus be characterised by the potential need for seasonal storage and use of synthetic fuels such as hydrogen. No countries are currently in this phase.

6.4 Priority Areas for System Transformation

The comprehensive transformation of the power system to achieve high proportions of VRE requires action in three main areas. These are:

- 1) system operation and market rules,
- 2) flexible resource planning and
- 3) investment, system-friendly VRE deployment.

A comprehensive set of policy, market and regulatory frameworks is needed to link actions in the three areas effectively. Importantly, the deployment of these measures has significantly broader benefits than simply promoting VRE integration rather, they help to boost power system operational efficiencies, reduce environmental impacts, promote investment and competition, and increase reliability and resiliency.

Figure 3. Three main pillars of system transformation

Notes: CID = contract for difference; DSR = demand-side response; FIT = feed-in tariff; PPA = power purchase agreement.

Power system transformation for achieving high shares of VRE has three main pillars.

1. **First Pillar:** System operation and market rules: Improved operating strategies are a powerful tool to maximise the contribution of existing assets to power system transformation. Relevant operating strategies include advanced renewable energy forecasting and enhanced scheduling and dispatch of power plants. In addition, new services for the power system (ancillary services) can become relevant, especially at growing shares of VRE. While markets for ancillary services are a key component, the most important market mechanism for system transformation is a well-functioning short-term (spot) electricity market. This provides a crucial basis for operating the entire power system much more dynamically, reflecting rapidly changing supply/demand patterns. Another important element for improved operations is expanding the geographic area over which demand and supply are balanced.
2. **Second Pillar:** Flexible resource planning and investment: Deploying a balanced mix of flexible resources is critical for the long-term evolution towards a transformed power system. As explained above, different technical options are available to provide power

system flexibility. The most widely used option today is the more flexible use of conventional power plants, combined with increases in grid infrastructure. However, digitalisation and the rise of distributed energy resources and systems open up radically new options to balance supply and demand.

3. **Third Pillar:** System-friendly VRE deployment: solar PV power plants themselves can also facilitate power system transformation, where policy allows and encourages them to do so. The classical paradigm for solar PV deployment emphasises generating the maximum volume of energy with little consideration for where and when it occurs. However, as solar PV play an increasing role on the system, planning and procurement strategies must take into account effects on the system. Power system transformation requires co-ordinated changes across the entire value chain of electricity production and consumption. Indeed, it may even necessitate the creation of entirely new roles in the power system, such as aggregators of small-scale power system assets (e.g. smart charging of a fleet of EVs in order to provide grid services). In practice, this means that it is not sufficient to look only at the technical or economic aspects of system transformation. The institutional setup and the roles and responsibilities of different stakeholders in the system require review and possibly revision. This is particularly relevant for establishing medium- and long-term system plans. Here it is critical for all stakeholders to ensure that planning entities operate in a transparent environment and work to promote fair market access and competition as plans are translated into reality.

6.6 Modelling Approach: Zambia Will Follow China's Blue Print Standing on the Shoulder's of Giants

Advanced energy modelling exercises highlight the possibility of achieving a transformed power system in China by 2035. Two different IEA scenarios describe possible configurations for the Chinese energy system in 2035.

1 This report elaborates on the main scenarios for China from the IEA *World Energy Outlook (WEO)*.

2 The two key *WEO* scenarios explored for China are the New Policies Scenario (NPS) and the Sustainable Development Scenario (SDS) (Figure 4).

The NPS aligns with the achievement of China's Document No. 9 reforms and aims to provide a sense of where today's policy ambitions seem likely to take the energy sector in China. In the

NPS, non-fossil technologies account for 60% of installed capacity and approximately 50% of generation. Wind and solar PV provide 21% of total generation. The NPS assumes a carbon dioxide (CO₂) price of USD 30/tonne. The WEO NPS assumes the implementation of economic dispatch, optimised trading and increased interconnection between provinces.

The SDS achieves the main energy-related outcomes of the Sustainable Development Goals, including delivering on the Paris Agreement, achieving universal access to modern energy by 2030, and reducing dramatically negative health outcomes due to energy-related air pollution. Its vision is aligned with the “Beautiful China” initiative proposed in the 19th National Congress of 2017 as the general blueprint of China’s future development. Under the SDS, nuclear and renewable technologies have higher levels of installed capacity, particularly wind, solar and hydropower, with less fossil fuel generation. Of the installed fossil fuel capacity, 15% has carbon capture and storage (CCS). Non-fossil technologies account for 74% of installed capacity and 72% of total electricity generation. Wind and solar PV account for 35% of total electricity generation. The SDS assumes a CO₂ price of USD 100/tonne. The WEO SDS assumes sufficient flexible resources to fully integrate VRE into the system.

Figure 4. Capacity and generation mix for China in 2035, IEA WEO NPS and SDS

The SDS introduces a greater proportion of renewables and a lower proportion of fossil fuel technologies compared to the NPS.

The modelling analysis presented in this report takes these *WEO* scenarios a step further. Building on a regional model developed for the *WEO 2017*, it features detailed power sector modelling analysis at an unprecedented level of detail to help understand the value of various policy and technology choices in the year 2035. The modelling highlights what aspects of the power system are most crucial in 2035 – this then allows the identification of priority areas for policy options. To achieve this, a regional model has been developed that includes a detailed bottom-up analysis of future demand structures, taking into account anticipated structural shifts in the Chinese economy.

The NPS is used to explore the value of current and proposed policies, notably the ongoing power market reform that foresees the introduction of spot markets and increased levels of cross-provincial trade. The analysis uses a two-step approach: first, an inflexible version of the NPS is modelled; then different options to make the system more flexible are analysed. The NPS analysis looks specifically at measures to improve system operation and market functioning.

The SDS is used to explore the importance of advanced flexibility options in particular on the demand side – to support a deeper transformation of the system. A two-step approach is also used for the SDS: first, an inflexible version is modelled; then different flexibility options are deployed in the system and their impact is analysed. The SDS provides a framework to assess the application of advanced technologies to provide flexibility. In both scenarios, the modelling finds that steps to increase the flexibility of the power system are crucial for unlocking the full potential of renewable energy for power system transformation.

6.7 Spot markets and regional trade

Establishment of spot markets and trade between provinces are two of the main elements to improve market rules and hence system operation in China.

6.8 Advanced Power System Flexibility

Activating the demand side, including EVs, and targeted use of electricity storage are crucial to delivering an accelerated transformation of the power system. Power system flexibility is the most important cornerstone of a transformed power system with a high share of VRE. In the SDS, VRE resources account for 35% of electricity generation on average. However, in some regions these numbers are much higher. For example, in the Northwest region VRE

covers 73% of electricity demand. This requires unprecedented levels of system flexibility, including advanced technologies to ensure system stability. Relying on advanced technologies enabled by digitalisation allows for the reliable integration of very high of variable generation without any excessive curtailment in 2035 under the SDS.

6.8 Advanced Technologies Enabled by Digitalisation – Reduce the Need to rely on Power Plants To Provide Flexibility.

The modelling under the SDS combines a broad range of advanced flexibility options. Their impacts have been estimated on the basis of detailed bottom-up modelling of future electricity demand in China, assuming that advanced technologies can unlock the flexibility potential. The assumed flexibility options for this report are:

1. Approximately 300 GW of residential, commercial, agricultural and industrial-sector load contributing to DSR programmes are in place in 2035, with enrolled resources spanning space heating and cooling, water heating, refrigeration and cleaning appliances.
2. 220 million EVs are made available under smart charging schemes in China in 2035, which corresponds to approximately 250 GW of peak EV charging load and 800 terawatt hours of total annual EV charging load.
3. Over 100 GW of pumped storage hydro and over 50 GW of battery energy storage are deployed. The benefits and costs of the different flexibility options are quantified for

Working in concert, these options can greatly improve the match between wind and solar PV supply and electricity demand. Indeed, the modelling analysis finds that these options can substantially reduce the need for flexible power generation – by 300 GW, or 30% of the total installed fossil fuel generation capacity under the SDS in 2035.

Figure 6. Benefits and costs of different advanced power system flexibility

Figure 6. Benefits and costs of different advanced power system flexibility options, SDS, 2035

Notes: CAPEX = capital expenditure; OPEX = operational expenditure.

Advanced power system flexibility measures can bring substantial benefits for power system transformation.

The Use of Advanced Flexibility Options is Found to be Highly Cost-Effective Compared to the SDS Without Their Presence. Using these options to their maximum potential could lead to total net savings of USD 64 billion annually. This considers both reduced operating costs (including CO2 emission costs at a price of USD 100/tonne) and avoided capital costs for power plants. This number accounts for the investment required to install advanced flexibility capabilities. Increasing power system flexibility beyond readily available options, such as coal power plants, is thus one of the most important priorities for facilitating the rapid transformation of the power system towards higher proportions of variable generation.

6.91 Renewable energy policy

Advanced Renewable Energy Policies That Focus on System Value Can Minimise Integration Challenges.

As the share of renewable energy grows in the power system, the interactions between renewables and the broader electricity system need to be considered in the design of renewable energy policies. This usually becomes evident through the emergence of “hotspots” of VRE

deployment, where penetration levels are much higher than the national average and integration challenges become significant. An initial approach to this issue is the geographic and technological diversification of VRE deployment. A variety of measures can achieve this, such as limiting permits for new installations in certain regions, differentiating remuneration levels regionally or by time of production, or giving specific incentives for smaller scale Installations: China has implemented a number of these options in the past years with some success. However, there are additional possibilities to enhance the system integration of renewables by use of deployment policies.

The concept of system value (SV) is critical in this regard. Considering the value of electricity to the overall system opens a new perspective on the challenge of VRE integration and power system transformation. The value of electricity depends on when and where it is generated, particularly in a power system with a high proportion of VRE. During certain times, an abundance of generation can coincide with relatively low demand in such cases, the value of electricity will be low. Conversely, when little generation is available and demand is high, the value of electricity will be high. The SV of a power generation technology is defined as the net benefit arising from its addition to the power system.

While the conceptual framework applies to all power generation technologies, the focus here is on wind and solar power plants. The SV is determined by the interplay of positive and negative effects arising from the addition. On the positive side are all those factors included in the assessment that lead to cost reductions; these include reduced fuel costs, reduced CO₂ and other pollutant emission costs, reduced need for other generation capacity, reduced water requirements and possibly reduced need for grid usage and associated losses. On the negative side are increases in certain costs, such as higher costs of cycling conventional power plant and for additional grid infrastructure. Spot markets can be a very useful tool for providing appropriate signals to VRE developers and operators.

By exposing VRE plants to the varying prices on the spot market, they can be encouraged to build power plants that generate as much as possible at times and in places where electricity is valuable and where prices are higher than average. However, such approaches need to strike a balance between creating an incentive for system-friendly deployment while also providing sufficient investment certainty. Advanced market premium systems such as the current system

used in Germany or auction mechanisms that factor in SV such as the Mexican clean energy auctions are examples of how this balance can be achieved

6.92 Moving Towards Vision 20230 Where We Want to Be?

Realising Optimised Planning

Five-year plan: Zambia must adopt a central planning system for its economy. Making five-year plans for all critical economic sectors.

7.0 Long-term strategy

The five-year plan is seen as a medium-term planning instrument. The government has to consider long-term planning for the energy sector. The “Energy Production and Consumption Revolution Strategy” must be used as broad guidance for all the energy five-year plans and policies (NDRC and NEA, 2016d). The Strategic framework must focus on four areas: energy consumption, supply, technology and institutions, with the latter incorporating the need for international energy co-operation. The overarching aim is to realise a more secure, sustainable, diverse and efficient energy future.

7.1 Demand Side Management/Demand Side Response

Demand-side management (DSM) in China is an administrative procedure taken by power generation companies and grid companies. DSM was particularly encouraged during the years 2003 to 2008, when electricity supply experienced a shortage in some regions (CEC, 2018). The three major means of demand response in China are:

1. **Load Shifting:** to adjust consumers’ energy consumption behaviour by using heat storage and energy storage devices, while applying peak-hour prices and interruptible load compensation.
2. **Energy Saving:** to encourage energy-saving bulbs and high-efficiency motors, pumps and transformers.

3. Power Generation Resource Replacement: to encourage high-efficiency energy resources.

7.3 Electricity storage: Benchmarking China's Move

After more than a decade of development, China's electricity storage industry has stepped into an important phase of transition from demonstration applications to early commercialisation. At the end of 2016 the operational capacity of China's electricity storage projects totalled 24.3 GW, with the vast majority coming from pumped storage hydro and only 243 MW from battery electricity storage. At the start of 2016, the installed capacity of battery electricity storage projects in operation stood at 101.4 MW, itself a year-on-year rise of 299%.

Lithium-ion and lead-acid batteries dominated battery storage; lithium-ion batteries made up the largest share at 59%, increasing by 78% compared with the previous year. The capacity of battery electricity storage projects in planning and under construction in 2016 was approximately 845.6 MW. As regards the application of electricity storage, capacity in the field of distributed energy storage registered the highest year-on-year increase of 727% in 2016, followed by growth of 523% in applications for renewable energy grid connection. The main storage application is in microgrids. As for regional distribution, new battery electricity storage projects are mostly located in Northwest and East China.

On 22 September 2017, the NDRC, the Ministry of Finance and three other ministries issued *Guidelines for Promoting the Development of Energy Storage Technology and Industry* (NDRC et al., 2017b). The document states that: "Demand-side distributed energy storage systems should be encouraged. Entry criteria for deploying demand-side energy storage systems should be laid down so as to guide and regulate the establishment of the system. Power companies with rights to manage distribution networks and eligible residential users should be encouraged to install energy storage. Local consumption ratios of distributed energy resources and demand response should be improved so as to lower energy consumption costs. Exploration of relevant business models should be encouraged."

7.4 Standing on The Shoulders of Giants Investing in the 100Kva Battery Inverter Packages

Moving towards “Vision 2030 Energy Transition” with Green Bonds, Sustainable Finance and Climate Change. We propose the following Aggregate Plans for Energy Storage Solutions useful for driving energy technology and Innovation, Navigating future energy supply and demand, Premapping energy geopolitics, Strengthening energy policy and governance, unlocking energy finance, Building energy system resilience, determining the power of systems and accelerating access.

We have three plans that can be adopted towards accomplishing “Vision 2030 Energy Transition” . The first Plan has a cost estimate of ZMW10,000,000,000 to be financed in five years through the instalment schedule of Build-on Capacity increasing by 200MW per annum amounting to an aggregate capacity of 1000MW after project completion in five years with the project lifecycle of 6000 circles. The following breakdown supports the statement above.

7.5 Aggregate Planning for Increased Capacity Alternatives 1000MW/ 500MW/ 250 MW Vision 2030

Purchase of Solar Storage Solutions

Budget Estimation Plan A: 1000 MW by 2030

Aggregate						
Instalment Plan		1000MW	\$			\$
Year on Instalment	Year	Capacity	Cost Estimation Per Unit	Required Number of Units	Number of	Total Cost Without Set Up
2026		200.00	38,520.00	2,000.00		77,040,000.00
2027		200.00	38,520.00	2,000.00		77,040,000.00
2028		200.00	38,520.00	2,000.00		77,040,000.00
2029		200.00	38,520.00	2,000.00		77,040,000.00
2030		200.00	38,520.00	2,000.00		77,040,000.00
Goal Accomplishment		1,000.00	192,600.00	10,000.00		385,200,000.00

7.6 Towards Vision 2030 Budget Estimate Plan A

The national budget can allocate approximately ZMW 10,000,000,000.00 towards Vision 2030. The aggregated amount is to be paid in amortized amounts of \$ 77,040,000.00 per year for the next five years. The project life cycle is 6000 cycles per unit installed.

To achieve capacity of 1000MW by 2030, entails allocating approximately \$385,200,000.00 more or less depending on economic order quantities and price adjustments from suppliers and contractual quantity discounts allocated to the economic order quantities that will reduce the annual ordering and holding costs for the next five years. With this plan the breakdown of the Generation Capacity per unit is as follows

5.2 Generation Capacity per Inverter

Aggregate Instalment Plan A: Year to Year Capacity Add On

Year on Year Instalment	MW Unit Production Per Inverter	Required Units Per Year	Total Generated MW
2026	0.1	2,000.00	200.00
2027	0.1	2,000.00	200.00
2028	0.1	2,000.00	200.00
2029	0.1	2,000.00	200.00
2030	0.1	2,000.00	200.00
Goal Accomplishment	0.5	10,000.00	1,000.00

1unit 100Kva inverter produces 0.1 Mega Watt real power. Installing 2000 units will produce $0.1 * 2000 = 200$ MW add-on to existing capacity per year. Adding the same capacity every year for the next five years would imply that by the year 2030, total installed capacity would be 1000MW with total number of units purchased 10,000 pieces. Alternatively, if the cost estimation for plan A is seemingly to expensive, making it economically challenging to adopt and implement. An alternative is Plan B and Plan C following below.

7.7 Budget Estimation Plan B: Capacity 500MW by 2030

Aggregate

Instalment Plan 500MW

Year on Instalment	Year	Capacity	Cost Estimation Per Unit	Required Number Units	of Total Cost of Product Per Annum
2026		100.00	38,520.00	1,000.00	38,520,000.00
2027		100.00	38,520.00	1,000.00	38,520,000.00
2028		100.00	38,520.00	1,000.00	38,520,000.00
2029		100.00	38,520.00	1,000.00	38,520,000.00
2030		100.00	38,520.00	1,000.00	38,520,000.00
Goal Accomplishment		500.00	192,600.00	5,000.00	192,600,000.00

An alternative to plan A is to reduce capacity by half. The National Budget can Allocate approximately ZMW 5,000,000,000.00 towards Vision 2030. The project life cycle is 6000 cycles per unit installed. To achieve capacity if 500MW entails allocating approximately \$192,600,000.00 more or less depending on economic order quantities and price adjustments from suppliers and contractual quantity discounts allocated to the economic order quantities that will reduce the annual ordering and holding costs.

7.8 Generation Capacity per Unit

Aggregate Instalment Plan: Year to Year Capacity Add On

Year on Instalment	Year	MW produced by 1 Unit	Required Units Per Annum	Total Generated MW
2026		0.1	1,000.00	100.00
2027		0.1	1,000.00	100.00
2028		0.1	1,000.00	100.00
2029		0.1	1,000.00	100.00
2030		0.1	1,000.00	100.00
Goal Accomplishment		0.5	5,000.00	500.00

1 unit produces 0.1 Mega Watt real power. Installing 1000 units will produce $0.1 * 1000 = 100$ MW add-on to existing capacity per year. Adding the same capacity every year for the next five years would imply that by the year 2030, total installed capacity would be 500MW with total number of units purchased 5,000 pieces. Alternatively, we can consider plan C if A and B are not feasible.

7.9 Budget Estimation Plan C: Capacity 250MW by 2030

Aggregate				
Instalment Plan	250MW	\$	Units	Aggregate Total
Year on Year Instalment	Year Capacity	Cost Estimation Per Unit	Required Number of Units	of Total Cost of Product Per Annum
2026	50	38,520.00	500.00	19,260,000.00
2027	50	38,520.00	500.00	19,260,000.00
2028	50	38,520.00	500.00	19,260,000.00
2029	50	38,520.00	500.00	19,260,000.00
2030	50	38,520.00	500.00	19,260,000.00
Goal Accomplishment	250.00	192,600.00	2,500.00	96,300,000.00

An alternative to the plans A and B is to reduce capacity by half twice. The National Budget can Allocate approximately ZMW 3,000,000,000.00 towards Vision 2030. To achieve capacity if 250MW by 2030, the government can embark on a project called “Vision 2030” entails allocating approximately \$96,300,000.00 more or less depending on economic order quantities and price adjustments from suppliers and contractual quantity discounts allocated to the economic order quantities that will reduce the annual ordering and holding costs.

8.0 Generation Capacity per Inverter

Aggregate Instalment Plan: Year to Year Capacity Add On

Aggregate

Instalment Plan

Year on Instalment	Year	MW produced by 1 Unit	Required Units Per Annum	Total Generated MW
	2026	0.1	500.00	50.00
	2027	0.1	500.00	50.00
	2028	0.1	500.00	50.00
	2029	0.1	500.00	50.00
	2030	0.1	500.00	50.00
Goal Accomplishment		0.5	2,500.00	250.00

1 unit produces 0.1 Mega Watt real power. Installing 500 units will produce $0.1 * 500 = 50$ MW add-on to existing capacity per year. Adding the same capacity every year for the next five years would imply that by the year 2030, total installed capacity would be 250MW with total number of units purchased 2500 pieces

8.1 Labour Planning

Potential Employment Opportunities for Positions

1. Preventive Maintenance
2. Breakdown Maintenance
3. Monitoring and Detection
4. Procurement
5. Human and Cultural Managers
6. Project Managers
7. Research and Planning
8. Parts Specialists

8.2 Employment Stability Process

Every employee recruited for this project will follow the policies of ZESCO at any given time.

8.3 Hold Employment Constant

Maintains a trained workforce and keeps hiring and layoff as well as unemployment cost at a minimum

8.4 Work Schedules

Dependant on the flexibility of the operation functions

9.0 Job Design

Specifies activities that constitute a task for an individual. The importance of job design as a management variable is the division of labor (Heizer & Render, 2011).

9.1 Plant Maintenance and Reliability Scheduling

The importance of maintenance and reliability is to maintain the capability of the system. Good Maintenance removes variability. Systems must be maintained to reach expected performance and quality standards. Maintenance includes keeping a system's equipment in working order. Reliability is the probability that a machine part or product will function properly for a specified time under stated conditions (Heizer & Render, 2011).

9.2 How Do We Get There?

9.3 Investing Decisions: Surety Bonds & Renewable Energy Projects

Renewable Energy is here to stay. Renewable Energy Developers (REDs) should consider how surety bonds can enhance deal structure and provide a more strategic use of company resources. There are several ways in which a surety bond may come into play when developing Renewable Energy. Below are some of the key areas where utilizing a financial instrument, such as a surety bond, may offer some assurances that make the deal more attractive for the parties involved.

9.4 Energy Storage Projects

Developing ways to store and maximize newly-generated energy is a time-sensitive component in the shift to renewable energy. Not only is storing excess energy during off-peak hours cost effective, it also helps stabilize the energy grid overall. With the anticipated demands on the grid, these Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) need to be built quickly and correctly. One way of doing that is to obtain Performance & Payment bonds from the Energy Procurement Contractor (EPC). This ensures the storage system is in place in a timely manner for the energy being generated (Performance bond), allowing REDs to meet or exceed the output expectations of the overall project. It also reduces the likelihood of a Mechanics' Lien against the project (Payment bond).

9.5 Power Purchase Agreements: This Power Purchase Agreement will be Between the State Financers (The Obligee, NAPSA, Private and Public Sector Banks / Private Parties as Investors and Bank of Zambia as Issuer and Underwriting Authority (The Surety) with the Off-Taker ZESCO as the Principal)

These agreements between the State, The Central Bank and purchaser of the energy (the “off-takers”) provide the basis for the amount of energy generated and the rate at which it would be purchased. There is often some form of financial security required to ensure the necessary energy is delivered, which is most often cash or a letter of credit. Surety bonds can be a more cost-effective option, while also preserving REDs’ cash with the reduction/elimination of collateral requirements typically seen in letters of credit. Established REDs should strongly consider having a Surety Program in place to provide them confidence in the terms they will receive for the bonds, as well as the overall capacity they have with the surety

9.6 Decommissioning Bonds:

Renewable Energy projects have a useful life, which means [theoretically] they will have to be removed one day. Many state and local jurisdictions require some form of security as an assurance the project will be removed when no longer viable. These obligations are far off, and tying up any capital for this type of security inhibits a REDs ability to continue building/growing their project pipeline. By using a surety bond, which is a “contingent” or “off-balance sheet” liability, both equity and working capital can be reserved for new projects.

9.7 Supply / Material Procurement:

This can work in two ways: 1) a RED may require a supply bond from their vendor to ensure the materials (panels, batteries, etc.) are delivered timely to complete the project, or 2) the REDs may provide a surety bond to the supplier in lieu of a cash deposit for the order. Given the overall demand and leverage suppliers currently have, the latter is the more likely of the two scenarios.

9.8 Interconnection Agreement:

Utility companies need to build and expand their infrastructure to support the addition of new Renewable Energy projects to the grid. In addition to the fees they charge, financial guarantees are necessary to ensure the capital they invest in connecting these new projects is eventually reimbursed. Surety bonds are one form of financial security utilities might accept.

Surety bonds have long been used in construction, and it makes sense that this would extend to the construction of the new energy projects we require today. Although the underwriting may differ slightly, it will still rely on the financial qualifications and creditworthiness of the party providing the bond as financial security. In many cases, this will be the Renewable Energy Developers. Establishing a Surety Program today can benefit REDs in numerous ways:

Clarity on the amount of surety credit available both per project and in aggregate. Having this understanding allows REDs to strategically build their project pipeline and have the confidence they will have the capacity needed to provide the required financial securities.

Consistency in cost of providing financial securities. By establishing a Surety Program, REDs will have a clear understanding of the rate charged to obtain the necessary bonds. These rates are based on the credit profile of the company / owners, which can eliminate other factors a bank may consider when pricing a letter of credit (i.e. deposit balances).

Enhanced marketing to customers. Obtaining bonds from a surety evidences the company has been prequalified and approved by a surety. An experienced third-party providing an indication they have confidence the RED can successfully complete the project and perform their obligations could be the difference when an end user selects a new partner.

A surety's involvement can make the claims process more efficient and provide protection to REDs. Surety bonds are not typically a pay-on-demand instrument like a letter of credit. The surety has an obligation to investigate any claim made against the bond, which means a RED may be better protected if a frivolous claim were to be submitted. The surety is also solutions-oriented, suggesting all parties will be more satisfied with the outcome if their ultimate goal is a finished project that performs as expected.

There are many factors to be considered when establishing a Surety Program. Working with a surety professional that understands both credit underwriting and the unique obligations associated with Renewable Energy Development will help companies capitalize on opportunities today, while developing a strong business plan for the many years of development that lie ahead. As with most things, it's better to start early to ensure the necessary support is in place when it is needed.

9.9 Financing Decisions

Public Sector Debt Funding

The Bank of Zambia must take a different approach and use their overall standing and covenant strength to borrow and fund the "Vision 2030" Project through the issuance of the surety bond. The borrowing is secured against the authority rather than specific projects. This approach usually provides cheaper overall finance with fewer hurdles to draw down funding than private sector alternatives. Long term interest rates available are similar to senior debt finance rates.

For the surety bond, Bank of Zambia acts as the surety, ZESCO becomes the principal servicing the Obligee or the state because they own the project.

10.0 The Central Bank to Implement Surety Bonds

10.1 What Is a Surety Bond and How Are the Parties Involved Defined?

A surety bond is a three-party agreement assuring the project owner (obligee) that the contractor (principal) will perform a contract in accordance with the contract documents. Surety is designed to prevent a loss. The surety prequalifies the contractor based on financial strength and construction expertise. Because the bond is underwritten with little expectation of loss, the premium is primarily a fee for prequalification services (Schubert, 2003).

10.2 What Are the Obligations of Each Party to the Bond?

Each of the parties has responsibilities related to each other party.

The principal has the duty to the obligee to perform its contract. The obligee likewise owes a duty to the principal to uphold its end of the contract, including payment in accordance with the contract terms. The surety has a duty to the obligee to take action under the terms of the bond if the principal defaults under the contract. But the obligee has a duty to fulfil its bargain under the contract, again, including payment of any sums due under the contract, but this time to the surety that performs. The surety and the principal also have duties to each other. The surety has the duty to determine whether the principal is in default, and abide by the terms of the bond and any agreement of indemnity. The principal must cooperate with any investigation of an allegation of default and reimburse the surety for any losses incurred due to the default of the principal on its promise.

10.4 Which Laws Require Bonding?

The Miller Act of 1935 (originally enacted in 1893 as the Heard Act) mandates performance and payment bonds for all federal public works contracts in excess of \$100,000 and payment protection, with payment bonds the preferred method for contracts in excess of \$25,000. local jurisdictions must enact legislation requiring surety bonds on public works over certain dollar amounts. These generally are referred to as “Little Miller Acts.” Many general contractors then require their subcontractors to obtain similar bonds to protect them from contractor default

10.5 What Are Attorney-in-Fact and Power of Attorney - Bank of Zambia

Most surety companies distribute surety bonds through the independent agency system. When a contractor or subcontractor needs a bond, the first step is to contact a surety bond producer, also known as an agent or broker. The producer generally receives power of attorney, i.e. the producer can sign bonds on behalf of the surety company for projects that fall within acceptable ranges established by the surety company. The attorney-in-fact is the holder of the power of attorney.

10.6 What Happens with a Claim on a Surety Bond?

When a claim is made on a bond, the surety must investigate the allegation of contractor default. The principal must cooperate with the surety and provide the information necessary for the surety to make a decision of whether it must perform under the bond. For example, the surety will examine the validity of the bond, whether notice of default was proper, whether there were material alterations or changes in the scope of the contract or gross overpayments, among other information. If the surety determines that its obligations have not become void, the surety will identify its course of action, which may include:

1. Providing financial or technical assistance to the contractor;
2. Arranging for a replacement contractor;
3. Re-bidding the project for completion;
4. Or paying the penal sum of the bond.

10.7 What Are Rights of Subrogation?

Subrogation is the surety's right to enforce a third-party's rights against the principal. The surety must have made a payment to the third party in order to exercise subrogation rights. If the owner declares the contractor in default and the surety completes the contract, the surety has rights to undispersed contract funds. The principal must reimburse the surety for any losses incurred due to the principal's default. If the surety determines that the allegation of default is wrong, the surety and principal stand together to oppose the obligee's claims. In addition to its subrogation rights, the surety also acquires protection against loss through the general indemnity agreement.

10.81 What Is a General Indemnity Agreement?

While a surety guarantees the performance of the principal to the obligee, the principal remains liable for its original obligation. If the surety must perform its duty to the obligee regarding the principal's contract, the principal is liable to reimburse the surety for that performance. Because many contracting firms do not have the capital to assure this repayment, most surety companies require a general agreement of indemnity (GAI) to be signed not only by the firm, but by individuals willing to support the firm. This might be the owner(s) of the firm, the spouse of the owner, a parent corporation or merely other individuals willing to put themselves on the line due to their belief in the firm. Under the GAI (sometimes called simply an indemnity agreement), the principal company and all people or other companies that sign are liable to repay the surety for amounts it pays on the company's behalf.

10.9 What Legal Benefits Does a Bond Provide Subcontractors?

Sureties provide three basic bonds on a construction project: the bid bond, the performance bond and the payment bond. The bid bond ensures that the contractor will enter into the contract for the terms of its bid and supply the required additional bonds. The performance bond ensures the contractor will perform the contract, including paying its subcontractors and suppliers, and the payment bond provides a direct claim for subcontractors for unpaid invoices to the contractor. Each of these bonds has legal benefits to subcontractors. If a subcontractor submits a proposal to a contractor to be included in a bid, the subcontractor wants to be sure that the contractor will enter into the contract if awarded.

The bid bond encourages contractors to do just that in order to avoid having to repay losses to the surety from their failure to do so. The performance bond ensures that if the contractor defaults on the project someone else will be there with sufficient funds to see that the contractor's obligation to perform is completed. Subcontractors value having the performance continue with someone able to reaffirm the subcontracts without having to rebid the work under public bidding laws. The payment bond has the most obvious legal value to subcontractors. If a contractor fails to pay for work properly performed by subcontractors, those subs have a direct claim against the surety for sums justly due. The sub does not have to obtain its money from the general, but can work directly with the surety. This direct right of claim is especially valuable on a public project where a sub cannot file a lien against the work.

11.0 Financing Structure for Vision 2030: Surety Green Bonds

Green bonds are a type of debt instrument that functions like a regular bond, but with a key difference: the funds raised are exclusively used to finance or re-finance projects that have environmental benefits, such as renewable energy, energy-efficient buildings, and sustainable water management. The "green" designation requires that the issuer commits to the use of proceeds for these specific projects and provides transparent reporting on fund allocation and the estimated impact of those projects.

How Green Bonds Work

11.01 Issuance (Proposed Issuer is Bank of Zambia):

A public or private entity (like a company, government, or multilateral institution) issues green bonds to raise capital.

11.2 Investment (The National Pensions Scheme Authority, State Owned Banks and Private Sector Banks are Target Investors):

Investors, such as institutional investors, pension funds, or asset managers, purchase these bonds, effectively lending money to the issuer.

11.3 Earmarked Funds:

The issuer receives the funds and commits to allocating them solely to eligible "green projects".

11.4 Returns:

In return for their investment, bondholders receive regular interest payments (coupons) and the return of their initial principal when the bond matures.

12.0 Transparency and Reporting:

A critical component is the issuer's commitment to transparency. This includes:

- **Frameworks:** Developing a framework for how proceeds will be used and ensuring projects align with the Green Bond Principles (GBP).
- **Reporting:** Publishing regular, detailed reports on the use of the green bond proceeds and the environmental impact of the financed projects.

13.0 Purpose of Green Bonds

➤ **Financing the Green Transition:**

Green bonds connect investors who want to support environmental goals with businesses and governments that need funding for sustainable initiatives.

➤ **Promoting Transparency:**

The principles emphasize transparency to ensure funds are directed to genuine environmental projects and to help investors track their impact.

➤ **Driving Sustainable Investment:**

They are a growing part of the broader bond market, offering a way to invest in projects that contribute to a more sustainable and low-carbon economy

14. Conclusion

The process of integrating the existing capacity with solar solutions is not only costly to start but also gradual as the phases of integration outlined. As more utilities are added, efficiency and effectiveness will increase by the same amount applied to the grid.

Implications for power systems as power system transformation continues, distribution grids may emerge as a central component of a clean, reliable and cost-effective energy system. mass enrolment of demand response, enabled by digitalisation and the effective integration of energy efficiency through intelligent end-use devices. However, co-ordination is required to achieve this. The possible effects of increased electrification of road transport on electricity demand, and consequently on power grids, are a case in point. If left unchecked, the growth in EVs could have a number of undesirable effects on the power system, such as increases in peak demand, overloading of distribution grids and increased difficulty in integrating VRE.

References

Bond Management Services. (n.d.).

China Power System Transformation. (n.d.).

Heizer, J., & Render, B. (2011). *Operations Management Edition 10 Jay Heizer, Barry Render (Pearson, 2011)*.

Jiang, H., Islam, · A Y M Atiquil, Gu, · Xiaoqing, & Spector, J. M. (123 C.E.). Education and Information Technologies Online learning satisfaction in higher education during the COVID-19 pandemic: A regional comparison between Eastern and Western Chinese universities. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10519-x>

Kalaba, K., Felix, Chilombo, A., & Kaoma, H. (2022). *Policy and legal framework for renewable energy in Zambia: Opportunities and challenges*. 10, 1–6.
www.climatecompatiblegrowth.com

Ministry of Finance and National Planning. (2022). Eighth National development Plan (8NDP) 2022-2026. *Ministry of Finance and National Planning*, 105.

Schubert, L. (2003). SPECIAL SECTION : SURETY BONDING Q & A THE LEGAL BASICS OF SURETY BONDS A : A : A : A : A : A : What Is a General Indemnity Agreement ? A : A : A : *Construction Executive*, November.

THE POWER SYSTEM IN ENERGY-POOR. (n.d.).